

tourist attractions, the state of the tourist infrastructure and tourist products of the region. Therefore there is an urgent necessity to research these aspects. It could become an impulse in the activation the tourist flow, the lever of the formation of a competitive tourist product of regional and local significance. It also gives a great opportunity to increase the investment attractiveness of the territory, to solve partly the issue of employment of the population and essentially fill the budgets of all levels.

The issue of tourist attraction of the Rozhysche district of the Volhyn region is investigated. The comprehensive evaluation of the tourist-recreational potential of the district has made. The main natural recreational tourist resources and the components of the historical and cultural heritage, which determine the tourist specialization of the studied area, have characterized. Balneological resources are represented by the deposits of sapropel, which makes it possible to develop sanatorium and spa treatment. An important structure-forming element of the natural resource potential are the water and forest recreational tourist resources. They could be used for the development of the various forms of ecological tourism. In the district function 11 objects of the natural reserve fund.

The analysis of the current state and possibilities for the development of tourism infrastructure in separate subsystems has conducted: placement establishments, food establishments, leisure establishments and consumer service, transport infrastructure, communication and information services. The coefficient of security by the placement of the temporary accommodation is 0.49 un./km² and it is the average in the region. The restaurant economy is represented by 44 establishments. To optimize the subsystem «nutrition establishments» it's necessary to follow the general tendency towards rebranding of non-competitive restaurant facilities in the alternative establishment. The subsystem "leisure facilities" is the weakest link in the tourist infrastructure on the explored territories. The main urgent problems in the Rozhysche district are providing the infrastructure improvement and the information management of the main attractive objects of historical and cultural heritage and of the natural reserve fund, which are the most popular among the tourists, the insufficient provision of the information about the tourist and recreational opportunities of the region. The main problems of the structural elements of the tourist infrastructure are identified. The suggestions of priority measures of optimization of tourist infrastructure as a tool for increasing the tourist attractiveness of the destination are presented.

Key words: *tourism, tourist infrastructure, tourist attractiveness, Rozhysche District, Volhyn Region.*

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DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE REHABILITATION-SOCIAL TOURISM IN UKRAINE

The issues of development of inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism in Ukraine and the world are considered, problems and prospects for the implementation of this area of rehabilitation in Ukrainian society, especially for an inclusive group of tourists with disabilities of various forms

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and nosologies, are identified. This issue is of particular importance in Ukrainian society given the significant increase in the number of people with disabilities as a result of hostilities in eastern Ukraine (the military, the civilian population of the occupied territories, internally displaced persons). Their rehabilitation requires special methods and professional rehabilitation approaches and measures, taking into account the length of their stay in the zone of military conflict and the level of stressful situations.

Key words: *rehabilitation, tourism, inclusive tourists, socium, people with disabilities, inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism, tourism.*

Formulation of the problem. In Europe, it is believed that accessibility is not only an opportunity for unhindered movement, but first and foremost, it is creating an environment in which a person with a disability is comfortable with himself felt, could communicate, study and work. There is practically no information about affordable tourism and expert research in our country, although this is a promising direction of the tourism industry for the rehabilitation of people with disabilities [4].

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problems of socialization and adaptation of people with inclusiveness to the environment are the subjects of scientific research as domestic (O. Beydyk, N. Bielousova, O. Lyubitseva, S. Bogdanov, G. Gavryushenko, A. Kolupayev, N. Nida, N. Sofiy, I. Yarmoshchuk and others), as well as foreign scientists (V. Preobezhensky, M. Mironenko, I. Tverdokhlebov, I. Zorin, S.Sesolkin, etc.).

Selection of previously unsettled parts of the general problem. The prospect of tourism development in Ukraine for the disabled fully reflects the definition of inclusive tourism as a tourist product, which involves the availability of this type as "rest for all." This will include adapting the infrastructure of the tourist centers and tourist industry objects to the needs of people with different nosologies, including the disabled, the elderly, their careers and members of families with young children, etc.

Formulating the purpose of the article. Therefore, the purpose of this article is to study the development and introduction of inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism in the Ukrainian tourist industry in the direction of providing tourist services for inclusive groups of tourists, especially people with disabilities.

Presentation of the main research material. In the system of development of the tourist sphere of the world, a special place today belongs to inclusive tourism as a segment of social tourism, which in Ukraine, unfortunately, is at the initial stage of development.

Inclusive tourism is a modern type of tourism that allows any person to be included in tourism activity, regardless of his physical abilities and subject to availability of tourist infrastructure objects [3].

Inclusive tourism structurally includes various types of rehabilitation and social services, namely: medical, psychological, psychological and pedagogical,

professional, labor, physical culture, sports, physical, social and other social and domestic activities [1;2].

About 7% of tourists from around the world are people with disabilities. Therefore, this type of tourism is gaining momentum all over the world, and the demand in the tourism market, accessible to all, will grow in the coming years [10, 17].

According to the requirements adopted by ETAN, tourism accessible to all, including [19]:

- barrier-free areas: infrastructure and facilities;
- transport: air, land, sea, river, railway;
- high quality of services: professional provision of services by hotel, restaurant, excursion bureau staff, etc.;
- additional tourist options (entertainment, exhibitions, attractions, etc.): the opportunity to participate in the activities of all tourists in these events and events;
- marketing and Internet services (booking system, websites): the most accessible information for everyone.

If only 7-8 years ago it was possible to find information only about specialized rehabilitation centers “for guests in wheelchairs”, and the “accessibility” badge for wheelchair guests could be seen next to the name only in several resorts, now, in the description of the hotels There are whole blocks of world resorts: rooms for wheelchair users, wheelchair guests and even ... for people with disabilities [18, 20]. Although foreign experts say that there is a lack of information to the interested audience about hotel accommodation, information about the travel company, and associations of people with disabilities. The biggest numbers of travel companies that are currently capable of providing services for people with disabilities with various nosologies are concentrated in the United States and Western Europe.

Modern social tourism is developing in the form of “associative tourism”, organized by trade unions of travel companies and social tourism associations, for which the main task was the organization of cheap travel for people with low incomes [12]. A significant role in the development of social tourism was played by municipal authorities, creating for this not only economic conditions (granting socially-oriented tourism business land privileges, tax privileges and other preferences), but also infrastructure – focused primarily on people with limited physical abilities [10]. That is why, in European countries, tourism for this category of citizens is common.

Many travel agencies offer their services in this area, having various specialized tourist programs and excursions for people with disabilities [6; 7].

Economically beneficial for the development of social tourism is not the presence of individual infrastructure elements, but the creation of a complete

(centralized) system that would ensure people's access to proper rest, and therefore to the effective restoration of physical and spiritual strength.

World experience shows that the mass nature of open-ended social tourism makes it profitable, increases employment, attracts investment in tourism directly on the ground, and at the same time tax revenues.

Thanks to tourism, many countries of the world are strengthening the economy of their countries, supporting this area by legislatively verified policies. Tourism, as an important social phenomenon of our time, actively influences the livelihoods of society and at the same time depends on it. At the same time, tourism performs another very important function – social rehabilitation in relation to people with inclusions [5; 13].

According to world statistics, now about 15% of the world's population is persons with disabilities [1]. In Europe, people with disabilities make up from 22 to 31% of the population, and in the USA – 17% of the population.

It is known that due to certain obstacles, people with disabilities travel less actively. At the same time, such trips make up 7-8% worldwide, 11% of all tourist trips are to Europe; 11% – for domestic tourism in the USA and Australia. At the same time, people with disabilities in the UK (37%) and Germany are the most actively traveling – 53%.

Inclusive tourism today accounts for 12% of world tourist flows. According to forecasts of the WTO (World Tourism Organization), by 2020 it is predicted that inclusive tourism will make up 22% of all tourism expenditures in the world [11].

Research in the post-Soviet space (Belarus, 2014, TSIITIN, in 2014, Kazakhstan, in 2016) indicates that about 30% of people with disabilities are engaged in business and participate in politics. Approximately 30% are people who belong to the middle class. They could travel if appropriate conditions were created for this [1].

Today, Ukraine continues the process of transition from a medical to a social model of disability, when the expression “everyone is different, but everyone is equal” means that the state has changed its attitude towards people with disabilities who want to integrate into society [19].

In Ukraine, at the beginning of 2016, the number of persons with disabilities was 27,40000 people (6.5% of the country's population). Modern statistics show that in 2018, 5.8% of the country's population (2,436.000 people) are people with disabilities, and this is every 18th citizen of the state. About half of the disabled are people with limited mobility (“wheelchair users” who are bedridden). Often they occupy an active life position, master new professions. The overwhelming majority are young people under the age of 40, and of these, about 170,000 are children [13].

In recent years, a new category of persons with disabilities has appeared in the country – participants and victims of ATO, and these are usually people of young,

working age – whose number, unfortunately, is progressively increasing. They require special treatment and qualified rehabilitation assistance, both psychological and social, for those types of rehabilitation that in our country do not yet have a clear structure and practical implementation [14].

The technologies of social work with military personnel and their families differ depending on the nature and depth of their social problems, largely determined by the composition of military personnel, the length of their military service and the level of stressful situations.

The most vulnerable to stressful situations are children. According to experts, immigrants face a double trauma: firstly, the need to level out the effects of stress associated with living in the occupied territories, in the combat zone, the need to leave their places of permanent residence; secondly, experiencing stress due to the need to adapt to new conditions. They are the ones who face additional specific problems, in particular, this is the lack of due attention from adults, the fulfillment of part of family responsibilities by children, which are not characteristic of war. According to the stress in children only aggravated. Therefore, the issue of harmonious internally family climate and psycho-emotional state of each family member in conditions of stressful impact remains relevant [8; 15].

Since July 2014, Kostiantynivka, Donetsk region, at the State Institution "Scientific and Practical Medical Rehabilitation and Diagnostic Center of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine", studies of the characteristics of the emotional and volitional sphere of the population living in the area of the ATO. The number of children was 1,450 (5-14 years). The psychodiagnostic tools are: the children's questionnaire of neuroses (S.S. Sednev, Z.B. Zbarsky, O.K. Burtsev) [17, p. 134-138]. According to the results of the study, the following features of the emotional sphere of the children's contingent were established.

The prevailing emotions in the population of the military conflict zone in the Donbas have been diagnosed: anxiety, irritability, aggression, and fears, reflecting a negative picture of the mental state of the population. The use of an integrated psychocorrectional approach for each family member has emotional disorders, increases the effectiveness of rehabilitation assistance.

One of the effective methods of overcoming the psycho-emotional state of a person, and especially children, is tourist travel.

Conclusions. For the period 2014-2018 There is a development of inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism in almost all developed countries of the world, with the practical provision of tourism services for inclusive tourists, including those for wheelchair users. They include the presence of a whole range of amenities on the beaches, in hotels, in transport, during excursion services, in catering establishments and the like.

In Ukraine, inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism is only gaining momentum as a social service. This process was preceded by the creation of the Association for Inclusive Rehabilitation and Social Tourism (Cherkasy), the holding of the Symposium, which discussed the main issue of providing rehabilitation services to inclusive tourists (Uman'), the creation of a research and experimental site with inclusive rehabilitation and social tourism on the basis of Cherkasy the development of tourist routes adapted for various categories of inclusive tourists (and especially for military personnel, handicapped people and children immigrants), conducting a number of tests using modern methods to obtain a holistic picture of the psycho-emotional state of people in the military conflict zone in eastern Ukraine, etc. And most importantly, there is a transition from a medical to a social model of disability when the expression “everyone is different, but everyone is equal” acquires a new meaning in modern Ukrainian society.

Taking into account the global experience, we can assume that inclusive tourism can be a powerful means of rehabilitation, the possibility of recovery, communication with people, the elimination of existing psychological barriers, and psychological satisfaction.

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Анотація

Белоусова Н. В., Новаковська І. О. Розвиток інклюзивного реабілітаційно-соціального туризму в Україні.

Розглянуто питання розвитку інклюзивної реабілітації та соціального туризму в Україні та світі, визначено проблеми та перспективи реалізації цієї галузі реабілітації в українському суспільстві, особливо для інклюзивної групи туристів з інвалідністю різних форм і нозологій.

Це питання має особливе значення в українському суспільстві, враховуючи значне збільшення кількості людей з інвалідністю внаслідок воєнних дій на сході України (військові, цивільне населення на окупованих територіях, внутрішньо переміщені особи). Їх реабілітація потребує спеціальних методів і професійних реабілітаційних підходів і заходів, враховуючи тривалість їх перебування в зоні військового конфлікту і рівень стресових ситуацій.

Ключові слова: *реабілітація, туризм, інклюзивні туристи, соціум, люди з інвалідністю, інклюзивний реабілітаційно-соціальний туризм, туристична сфера*